

THE NOTION OF SYNCHRONIC TRANSLATION, ITS HISTORY OF DEVELOPMENT AND THE EXTENSION OF ITS USAGE

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ABSTRACT

General concepts related to synchronic translation illustrate that it is very broad area of oral translation. In the following article, we are going to discuss general information dealing with this branch of translation, in which we look into the emergence of simultaneous interpretation as well as considering the differences between the types of oral translation. And we try to highlight theoretical basis of simultaneous interpretation which were presented by the scientists who even currently work as professional interpreters. Now that the huge demand for simultaneous interpretation is increasing, it is incredibly essential to gain fundamental background on the synchronic translational methods, techniques, ways and peculiarities. In this article, we also try to look back into the history and developmental way of the synchronic translation. Besides that, we get acquainted with what kind of factors affected to the appearance of this type of oral translation. In this line we also spot the main differences of simultaneous and consecutive interpretation.

Key words: simultaneous interpretation, target language, consecutive translation, source language, oral translation.

INTRODUCTION

It is noteworthy to mention that at the present time, the common usage, and significance of synchronic translation is increasing immensely. By attaching a great hope to the popularization of our mother tongue, and in order to see our Uzbek language among the world's famous languages, the direct translating activity which involves the translation without any assistant language, is developing rapidly. For a long time, written translation has been of major importance in our country. But during the last few years, on account of modern-day demands, the area of oral translation, namely synchronic translation, is commencing the new era of translation in our country.

METHODS

Synchronic translation is a field of translation which is gaining a huge essentiality among the world community. Large demand towards this area of translation refers to the vital importance of its usage, as synchronic translation is regarded as one of the most productive ways of translating. Many international conferences, meetings, and sports events cannot be imagined without the use of synchronic translation.

Object of research can be observed in the practical and theoretical issues related to synchronic translation. The ideas and experiences of one of the first synchronic translators Siegfried Ramler, Gile, Al-Salaman, Al-Khanji, Jones and many other eminent scholars are supplemented as the main scientific object of the theme. Furthermore, synchronic techniques and experiences by James Nolan give additional standpoints to the perspectives of synchronic translation field. The views of Doctor of Philosophy Cronin, M. enable to clarify the actual problems that can be met during synchronic translation. Valuable views of scholars such as Daniel Gile and Al-Salmon are taken as the most important object of this research paper.

Before speaking about synchronic interpretation, it would be appropriate to mention about the actual meaning of the word “synchronic”. The verbatim translation of this word in language refers to linguistic phenomenon which occurs at a specific point in time [1]. Speaking in a nutshell, synchronic translation denotes conveying understanding. Another term for the synchronic translation which is commonly used by the world community is “simultaneous interpretation”. Its usefulness stems from the fact that a speaker’s meaning is best expressed in his or her native tongue but is best understood in the languages of the listeners. In today’s world, in the field of philology there is a kind of misunderstanding to differentiate the translation and interpretation. Many people consider that these above mentioned terms denote the same meaning, but it is absolutely wrong. Well, how does interpretation differ from translation? A translator studies written material in one language (the source language) and reproduces it in written form in another language (the target language). An interpreter listens to a spoken message in the source language and renders it orally, consecutively or simultaneously, in the target language. Both the translator and the interpreter must have a thorough mastery of the target language, as well as a very good passive understanding of the source language or languages with which they work [2]. For most interpreters, the target language will be his or her native tongue. The translator relies mainly on thorough research with background materials and dictionaries in order to produce the most accurate and readable written translation possible. The interpreter relies mainly on the ability to get the gist of the message across to the target audience on the spot.

RESULTS

No translation is ever “perfect” because cultures and languages differ. However, in practice, the translator is usually held to a higher standard of accuracy and completeness (including the ability to reproduce the style of the original), while the interpreter is expected to convey the essence of the message immediately. The translator’s activity is more like that of a writer, while the interpreter’s performance is more like that of an actor. A good translator will spend much time searching for the correct technical term or the right choice of words, but a good interpreter must immediately come up with a satisfactory paraphrase or a rough equivalent if appropriate term does not come to mind, in order not to keep the audience waiting. Some people are able to do both translation and interpretation. Others find that, for reasons of temperament and personality, they cannot do one or the other. Generally, some experience as a translator provides a good foundation for becoming an interpreter. Synchronic translation is the most complex one among the oral translation, in which translation is conducted with the help of special devices. It is a kind of popular and common way which is used during the process of interpretation in order to deliver the entire and constant meaning of a speaker’s words without any interference [3].

DISCUSSION

Researches on synchronic interpretation were conducted completely separately from other practical linguistic researches. That is because of the methodological problems emerged from the existence of multiple languages and various situations. The need to master this type of translation demanded new methods and special techniques, as the significance of synchronic translation increased rapidly in the last few years. Therefore, new methods, techniques and scientific works on simultaneous interpretation were initially created by those who once worked as professional interpreters. Nevertheless, it has been more than 50 years since the time when the first research analysis were held in the sphere of simultaneous interpretation, it is still unknown what kind of paradigm is suitable for this type of translation. Because of noble features of synchronic translation, scientists working on simultaneous interpreting had to produce various theoretical opinions of their own. First of all, the scientists emphasized to make use of synchronic translation into several existent modes. In the first place, they tried to synchronize the process of listening and speaking successfully. Secondly, the scientists who are expert at differentiating the semantic and structural gap between languages underlined the preciseness and momentary phenomenon of discourse in synchronic translation. The results of scientific research

showed that synchronic translation, in some ways, is both characteristic of written and oral forms of speech. Furthermore, research work discovered the differences of simultaneous interpretation which separates it from written form of speech and indicated what kind of further study is needed [4].

According to James Nolan in terms of the form of speech, oral translation is divided into two main types: simultaneous and consecutive translation. There is a huge gap between these types of oral translation. A consecutive interpreter listens to the speaker, takes notes, and then reproduces the speech in the target language. Depending on the length of the speech, this may be done all at one go or in several segments. The consecutive interpreter relies mainly on memory, but good note-taking technique is an essential aid. A simultaneous interpreter, usually sitting in a soundproof booth, listens to the speaker through earphones and, speaking into a microphone, reproduces the speech in the target language as it is being delivered in the source language. Because the simultaneous interpreter cannot fall too far behind, this method requires considerable practice and presence of mind. Consecutive interpretation was long the standard method, until simultaneous interpretation was first tried out on a large scale, and found to be workable, at the Nuremberg trials.

Thanks to that breakthrough and to modern sound equipment, simultaneous interpretation has now become the most widely used method, in every type of meeting from business conventions to summit conferences, and can even be done via remote communications links. It is much less time-consuming and enables a multilingual conference, with participants speaking a number of languages, to proceed without interruption. However, consecutive interpretation is still preferred in certain situations, such as one-on-one interviews, confidential hearings, brief public appearances by prominent persons, or some legal proceedings [5]. It has the advantage of not requiring much equipment. Darò, Valeria and Franco Fabbro outlines that interpreters may be asked to do “whispering” or “chuchotage”, which consists of sitting behind a participant at a meeting and simultaneously interpreting the proceedings only for that person. Simultaneous interpreters normally work in teams of two per booth, taking turns in shifts of about 30 minutes each for a maximum of about three hours at a time, which has been found to be the maximum average time during which the necessary concentration and accuracy can be sustained [6]. They generally work only into their “A” (best) language, or their mother tongue. In certain situations (e.g. in a meeting where one language largely predominates), a single team of three people, known as a “petite equipe”, will work both ways, rather than two booths of two people each [7]. The number of languages spoken at the meeting may also determine the make-up of the team. In the United Nations, for example, the standard “English booth” team

consists of two interpreters, one of whom interprets from Russian, one of whom interprets from Spanish, and both of whom can interpret from French. For certain language combinations, relay, or two-step, interpretation is also sometimes used: a speaker will be interpreted in one booth from language A into language B, and then in another booth from language B into language C [8].

For the first time in the history, the synchronic translation was used in Germany in 1946 after the Second World War during the process of International Nuremberg Trials in order to prosecute criminal acts of Nazis. That was the time when simultaneous interpreting was firstly used in such a widely-scaled meeting [9]. Because of the subsequent emergence of International Organizations after the Second World War, the demand for an effective type of translation increased very quickly. When the idea of using synchronic translation as the most effective and suitable tool came into being, language critics were skeptic to the appropriateness of using it into practice. However, after the presentation of the potential advantages of synchronic translation, new programs were immediately created in order to prepare simultaneous interpreters. The first representatives of synchronic translation researchers had to set professional and academic norms of synchronic translation. Primary manuals on synchronic translation such as Rozan 1956 and Herbert 1965 were created as a result of challenging researches and they are still deemed as the classic notes of simultaneous translation. Apart from the simultaneous interpreters and the people who still link their lives with synchronic translation, there are some people who think that synchronic translation is not suitable and effective. One of the eminent scholars such as Christoffels, I. K. & De Groot stated that the language of discourse culture and the concepts which were dominant at that time like, structuralism and behaviorism were a large threat to simultaneous translation.

Jones, R. states that apart from being used widely in international conferences, simultaneous translation is used in diplomatic activities, in the field of trade, mass-media, education, in the system of justice and etc. Synchronic translation is mainly used in the United Nations. There are six official languages in this organization, they are: English, French, Russian, Spanish, Chinese and Arabian. These languages possess equal reputation in the UN, and during the speeches, the delegates can choose any one of them. However, daily secretarial duties of the UN are run by English and French languages. Any kind of formal conferences of the UN are conducted in above-mentioned six languages and documents as well as formal speeches are published in six appointed languages. The sphere of synchronic translation is regarded as a field which has very few working staff. In addition, the sphere of synchronic translation is counted as one of the most difficult professions for which it is completely difficult to

prepare personnel [10]. According to Gerver David, there are only more than 2000 professional personnel in this sphere. Although English has already become widely-used language and mastered by great number of learners, there is still lack of born talents who can be experts in the field of synchronic translation. It is almost impossible to find simultaneous interpreters who work especially in the English, French, Russian and many other minor languages in our country. Simultaneous interpreters who are comprehensively-developed, namely who have broad understanding in politics, trade, technology and other fields are extremely rare. The amount of money that is paid to synchronic interpreters is not measured by a monthly salary, on the contrary, it is measured by the day, hour and minute they work. For example, in China simultaneous interpreters of the English language are paid 1200-1800 Yuan for a day. According to Gile, Daniel, simultaneous interpreters work in groups which consist of 2-3 members. The daily amount of paid money that was shown above is divided between the members of a group. Therefore, the hirer of interpreters doesn't have any right to meddle how to arrange the working-days and day-offs of simultaneous interpreters. Thus, in China daily profit of a simultaneous interpreter comprises at least 4000 Yuan. In Russia, simultaneous interpreters are paid 4000-7000 rubles for per hour and 20000-30000 rubles for per day. It's not always possible to find and book an available simultaneous interpreter because of a huge demand for them. Besides that, simultaneous translators don't tend to receive the orders of unexamined clients, but in such cases they can negotiate with above-mentioned un-examined clients relying on the advice of their colleagues. If the profession and the service of simultaneous interpretation is far more demanding and expensive than consecutive interpretation, a question arises in this way: why is simultaneous interpretation broadly-used though? In respond to this question, Dam, Helle V. says that simultaneous translation saves the time while in consecutive translation the time is naturally prolonged and the excessive expenses of the rent of conference hall, accommodation and food for guests becomes tremendously expensive for the hirer of consecutive interpreters.

During simultaneous translation, it is very important to have necessary equipment, which helps to facilitate the process. Special equipment like earphones and microphones constitute the system of simultaneous translation and it can be as a stationary or moveable booth [11]. In the conferences, simultaneous interpreters are placed in small isolated booths and they wear special earphones in order not to surpass the speaker's voice. With the help of loudspeakers, the interpretation is transmitted to the ears of speakers. Such sorts of interpretations which require technical equipment are conducted in the summit conferences, auditoriums and other events where there are large numbers of participants. In every congress and conference hall of the UN, there

is installed a system of simultaneous interpretation. There is a working booth for every single language. It means that if there are six official languages in the UN, there are six isolated booths, respectively and three interpreters in every booth.

The most significant strategies that are used in simultaneous translation have also been thoroughly learned and analyzed in the condition of Uzbek and English language. In addition, the problematic matters between Turkish and English have been investigated and the solutions to the most essential issues have been considered as the perspectives of simultaneous interpretation in the developmental stage of the profession in Uzbekistan.

The issue of untranslatability is regarded as the main issues in interpreting process in Uzbek language, therefore, some important solution have also been found out in this research paper. A number of important limitations need to be considered. The most important limitation of this sphere is the unavailability of more data for analysis. More renditions would have provided more data for analysis, and therefore, better results have been aimed in the outcome of the research. Another limitation of field is the constraint of time. More time would have made it possible to include more than one issue and solution, which would have allowed for wider research on this issue.

CONCLUSION

Finally, this article itself does not offer conclusive findings on the subject of interpreter's strategies in political discourse, especially given the absence of literature on the subject. However, the supplied date can hopefully be used as a point of departure for further and wider research on the subject, with the aim of avoiding misunderstandings, which is stated are not only the products of linguistic incompatibilities, but of cultural ones as well

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